

Tungro (RTV) development in rice

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We studied the development of RTV infection in rice varieties with different levels of resistance to the vector green leafhopper (GLH). In a wet season trial Aug-Oct 1985, high infection by rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) was

28 DT, coincidental with detection of RTBV + RTSV. RTSV infection rate was highest about a month after transplanting, and decreased thereafter, whereas infection with RTBV + RTSV increased remarkably 1 mo after

1. Percentage of RTBV and RTSV infection assessed by latex test in 6 rice varieties at different times after transplanting, IRRI. WS = wet season, DS = dry season.

2. Percentage of RTBV and RTSV infection assessed by latex test, and RTV incidence based on symptoms in variety TN1 at different times after transplanting. IRRI, 1987 DS.

found 30 d after transplanting (DT) in all varieties except IR54 and IR58, which have GLH resistance. RTSV infection remained high to the end of the test period, except in susceptible TN1 and IR22. Infection with both RTSV and rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) was high in TN1 and IR22.

In a similar trial Jan-Mar (dry season) 1986, RTSV infection at 30 DT was low even in TN1 and IR22. Infection increased slowly with both viruses in all varieties. RTV development was more rapid in susceptible TN1 and IR22 than in moderately resistant IR36 and IR42. IR54 and IR58 had low infection, regardless of cropping season (Fig. 1).

In the Jan-Mar 1987 trial using TN1 plants, RTSV infection occurred as early as 14 DT. RTV symptoms appeared at

transplanting (Fig. 2).

The rate of RTV development varied among varieties and cropping seasons. RTSV infection could occur soon after transplanting, about a month before appearance of RTV symptoms. RTSV incidence also varied with cropping season. □

Stability of bacterial blight (BB) resistance in IR varieties

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Eleven IR varieties were evaluated for BB resistance at AanRen, Hunan, 1975-